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Examination Of Election Management In Nigeria's Fourth Republic

¹NDUBUISI, O. Johnson PhD & ²NWOGUEZE, Chinweuba

¹Department of Political Science,
Novena University, Ogume, Delta State, Nigeria

²Ph.D Candidate, Department of Political Science,
Novena University, Ogume, Delta State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study examines the role of security agencies in policing elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic, highlighting their effectiveness, challenges, and contributions to democratic governance. Since the transition to civilian rule in 1999, elections in Nigeria have been characterized by multidimensional security threats, including violence, intimidation, and manipulation of electoral processes. Security agencies, primarily the Nigerian Police Force and the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), have been tasked with ensuring election security, protecting electoral materials, monitoring campaigns, and maintaining law and order. While these agencies have played crucial roles in preventing large-scale violence and facilitating peaceful electoral transitions, their involvement has sometimes been marred by partisanship, corruption, inadequate training, and misuse of authority, which undermines public confidence in the electoral process. Challenges such as limited resources, political interference, rising insurgency, banditry, and separatist movements further complicate effective election policing. Using a historical research design and qualitative analysis of secondary data, the study reveals that professional integrity, neutrality, adequate resourcing, and functional autonomy are critical for enhancing the effectiveness of security agencies in Nigeria's elections. The findings underscore the need for strengthened institutional mechanisms to ensure that elections are conducted freely, fairly, and credibly, thereby consolidating democracy in Nigeria.

Keywords: policing elections, Nigeria's Fourth Republic,

INTRODUCTION

What makes democratic governance the most preferred system of government today is the institutionalisation of periodic elections. The conduct of credible elections on a typically political party basis is the preferred means of choosing elective public office holders. This underscores the essence of democracy and periodic elections in any modern state. Free, fair and credible election is unavoidable *sine qua non* for any democratic state. Additionally, free, fair and credible election does not only encompass total objective and behaviour of the governmental agency concerned with the conduct of elections, but embodies legal or constitutional processes of selection and recruitment of government officials, including members of the executive and legislative arms of government. Appadorai (2004), and Onyishi, Oji and Ugwuanyi (2023) in related manners defined ideal democracy as a system under which the citizens periodically exercise their franchise to choose their representatives, as well as protect their collective interest as a people. Ideal democracy thus agrees with the notion that concerns

management of modern society and provides enabling social institutions. It also promotes popular will, especially in areas that concerns social direction and public policy.

As Ali and Ali (2022:1) rightly stated “the role of the people in a modern society is to produce a responsible government, but the only way to achieve this is through competitive elections which stand in as an institutional framework for arriving at political decision in which individuals acquire powers”. As the fundamental building block of democracy, election plays fundamental role in sustenance of political behaviour. The only way to ensure that the right kind of leadership emerges is through free, fair and credible elections (Okolo, 2002), regrettably, the First and Second Republics that are the pillars upon which Nigeria’s post-independence democracy stands, and the faulted Third Republic were short-lived due to a number of factors such as weak political institutions, poor economic situations, and ethnic divisions, rise of authoritarian leaders, post-election violence, and annulment of concluded elections by the military government. The early years of post-independence era were characterised by military coups that lasted for several years (Erunke, 2012; Ediriverere, 2023).

While Ugwu and Omotola (2023) identified intimidation, the use of armed groups to intimidate voters, the use of state security agencies to suppress opposition parties, and the use of propaganda and disinformation to manipulate public opinion among the multidimensional election security threats as the major threats associated with political violence in Nigeria, Alao (2021:320) argued that these challenges have undermined the integrity of electoral processes and confidence of voters in the fairness and legitimacy of elections in Nigeria under the Fourth Republic. Election in Nigeria, though, is traced to the Clifford Constitution of 1922 which allowed for the first time, elective principles, but it was for a selected few. It laid the foundation for increased representation in governance in subsequent constitutions, and was the first time Africans were elected into the legislature of a British territory in tropical Africa (Alao, 2021:320). It implies that Nigeria’s democracy has a long history, as it has election challenges resulting in election security threats. On 1 October 1960, the federation of Nigeria gained her independence from Britain and became a member state of the Commonwealth of Nations (CON). The independent Nigeria had the founder of the Northern People’s Congress (NPC), Abubakar Tafawa Balewa as the Prime Minister; and Dr. Benjamin Nnamdi Azikiwe, the leader of the National Council of Nigeria and Cameroon (NCNC) appointed the Governor-General (the representative of Queen Elizabeth II) on 16 November 1960. On October 1, 1963, the Federal Republic of Nigeria was created with Belewa as the first Prime Minister, and Azikiwe as the President (Clay, 2024).

On 8 December 1964, President Azikiwe dissolves the House of Representatives. On 30 December 1964 and 18 March 1965, parliamentary elections were conducted with NPC having 162 seats out of 312 in the House of Representatives, while NCNC won 84 seats in the House of Representatives. The United Progressive Grand Alliance (UPGA) boycotted the parliamentary elections. Another valid example of election violence-prone insecurity involved the Western Regional election of 11 October 1965, in which Chief Samuel Akintola of the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) was re-elected as the Premier of Western Region. The post election violence that followed the victory of Akintola led to the killing of 160 civilians and 7 police officers. On 12 January 1966, 20 civilians were also killed in another political violence in Ilesha (Clay, 2024). This multidimensional electoral security challenge in Nigeria explains why Omotola (2010:535) observes that election has been one of the main problems of democratisation process in Nigeria. Above all, it was this dire security dilemma during elections in Nigeria that necessitated the drafting of security agencies to police elections. The extent to which these elections are effectively policed is the burden of this study.

Objectives

1. Ascertain the extent to which the security agencies have effectively police elections in Nigeria’s fourth republic,
2. Identify the problems created by the security agencies during election policing in Nigeria’s fourth republic, and
3. Analyse the challenges facing the security agencies in the course of election policing in Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. To what extent have the security agencies effectively police elections in Nigeria's fourth republic?
2. What are the problems created by security agencies during elections policing in Nigeria's Fourth Republic?
3. What are the challenges facing security agencies while policing elections in Nigeria's fourth republic?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Evolution of Democratic Election in Nigeria

Explaining the history of the largest democracy in Africa, Nigeria, cannot be concluded without a mention of its fragile and fluctuating democracy since independence in 1960. Successive governments struggled to create a sense of national unity in a complex nation where borders were drawn by British colonialists that merged more than 200 ethnic groups in 1914. Nigeria democracy also has a troubled relationship with the military for almost half of its existenc as an independent state. Three Republics were overthrown by military coups since independence, and two of the democratically elected presidents of the Fourth Republic headed those military dictatorships, precisely General Olusegun Obasanjo and General Muhammadu Buhari respectively. The present experience stems from the 1999 election when Chief Olusegun Obasanjo was elected under the People's Democratic Party (PDP) (Hoffmann & Wallace, 2023; Edirinverere, 2023). Lugman (2009:59) argued that, "while a great deal of the problems confronting elections and electoral process in Nigeria's democratic history is linked to behavioural and attitudinal disposition of the political elite, a substantial portion of the blame must be placed on the door step of INEC that is saddled with the responsibility of conducting elections".

Democratic election in Nigeria is traced to the Clifford Constitution of 1922 which allowed for the first time, elective pinciples, although this provision was for a selected few but it laid the foundation for increased representation in governance in subsequent constitutions. Indeed, this was the first time Africans were elected into the legislature of a British territory in tropical Africa. It implies that Nigeria's democracy has a long history as it has conduct of election challenges, resulting in election security threats. It is however evident that one recurring phenomenon in the unending saga of violence in Nigerian democracy is electoral violence, which began with the First Republic and continues till the present Fourth republic democratic dispensation (Alao, 2021:320). Judging from this note, Nigeria has not been fortunate to conduct free, fair and credible elections. On 1st of October 1960, the Federation of Nigeria gained her independence from Britain and became a member state of the Commonwealth of Nations (CON). The independent Nigeria had the founder of the Northern People's Congress (NPC), Abubakar Tafawa Balewa as the Prime Minister; and Dr. Benjamin Nnamdi Azikiwe, the leader of the National Council of Nigeria and Cameroon (NCNC) appointed the Governor-General (the representative of Queen Elizabeth II) on 16 November 1960.

On 1 October 1963, the Federal Republic of Nigeria was created and for the first time had a Nigerian, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa as the Prime Minister, and Dr. Benjamin Nnamdi Azikiwe as the President. Subsequent development saw President Azikiwe dissolved the House of Representatives on 8 December 1964. Further development ushered in the 30th December 1964 and 18 March 1965 parliamentary elections with NPC having 162 seats out of 312 in the House of Representatives, while NCNC won 84 seats in the House of Representatives, and the United Progressive Grand Alliance (UPGA) boycotted the parliamentary elections. On 11 October 1965, Chief Samuel Akintola of the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) was re-elected as the Premier of Western Region. The post election violence that followed the victory of Akintola led to the killing of 160 civilians and 7 police officers. On January 1966, 20 civilians were also killed in another political violence in Ilesha (Clay, 2024).

The trajectory of Nigeria's political evolution since independence in 1960 has been deeply intertwined with military intervention and influence, creating a longer regime of military in power. In 1966, the

country experienced a military coup which set off series of military takeovers that dominated its landscape for decades, often justified by the need to maintain order and stability amid political corruption and civilian incompetence. The justification frequently marked deeper issues of power consolidation and authoritarian control (Openiyi, 2020). Today, the military is a critical actor in the country's security landscape, engaged in various operations to combat Boko Haram in the North-East, addressing banditry in the North-West, and separatist agitations in South-East region. Transition to civilian rule in 1999 marked a significant milestone in Nigeria's political development. It has left the issue of civil-military relations pertinent as the military continues to play a vital role in addressing internal security challenges such as insurgency, terrorism and communal violence. Beyond these internal security issues, the military has been engaged in election exercise to ensure the safety of voters and officials of the electoral umpire and electoral materials (Oyewole, 2020; Matthew, 2023).

Evolution of Political Parties in Nigeria

The evolution of party politics in Nigeria dates back to the days of the struggle for political independence from the British colonial masters. Since independence in 1960, political party formation has always presented certain challenges, with ethnic and religious sentiments often attached. Under British colonial rule which lasted from 1914 to 1960, the first regime of party politics adopted the Western-Styled parliamentary democracy. The manifestation of this regime of party politics was witnessed under the political activities of the amalgamated Nigeria, particularly in 1922 and 1923 when elections and a political party, the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) was formed (Mustapha & Isah, 2018: 117). It is important to note that Nigeria's politics has taken place within a framework of a federal, presidential and representative democratic republic in which executive power was exercised by the government while legislative power was in the hands of the National Assembly: the Senate and the House of Representatives in independence in 1960 up to the present time (McMillan, 2010).

The nation's politics has also experienced *diarchy or diarchism*, a form of political arrangement that is partly dictatorial and partly constitutional and which is associated with military government. The term "Diarchism" is used to describe a form of government in which the supreme powers of the state is vested in the hands of two groups of people, i.e., the men on uniforms (military men) and those on muftis (civilians). It is also the sharing of power between the military personnel and the civilians in government (McLean & McMillan, 2010; Okereka, Efebeh, Ikenga & Oluka, 2020). Section 229 of 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) specifically defined political party as the organisation that preoccupies itself with soliciting for votes during elections into various political offices. From the 1940s when the nationalists started to agitate for the inclusion of Nigerians in the governance of the indigenous people of the country, party politics has taken multiple dimensions and divergent development (Dobie, 2012: 97).

On 24 June 1923 the first political party, the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) was formed by Sir Herbert Macaulay to advance the case of the nationalists for their inclusion into the colonial government. This development was fostered by Sir Clifford Constitution of 1922 which succeeded the 1914 Lord Lugard Amalgamation Constitution. The NNDP successfully won three seats in the Lagos Legislative Council in 1922, and all the seats in the elections of 1923, 1928 and 1933. Among the first generation parties in the country were the Action Group (AG) formed by Obafemi Awolowo, and Nigerian Youth Movement (NYM) formed by Samuel Akintola in 1935 and also featured prominent characters like Ernest Okoli and Dr. C. Vaughan. Nnamdi Azikiwe, H. O. Davis and Obafemi Awolowo later joined the movement which later became a full blown political party and competed fervently with NNDP, particularly in the 1960s (Meredith, 2005; Okereka et al., 2020).

The Multifaceted Challenges in the Management of Elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

Since 1999, the democratic space in Nigeria has been dominated by political shenanigan for underhand purpose chiefly for power retention by power political elites. These elites consistently dominate the political space and in the end violate fundamental principles associated with a liberal democratic system, such as competitive elections, the rule of law, and political competitive, and respect for human

rights. The outcomes of the 2019 and 2023 presidential election further eroded public trust in the ability of INEC to organise competitive elections unfettered by the authoritarian influences of the ruling class. This challenge is an indicator of the systemic failure in Nigeria's governance system. With the current system in which votes are attained through empty promises, bribery, voter intimidation, and violence, Nigeria needs a governance system that will enhance the education its voters and the capability of its leaders. Political elites in Nigeria also exploit poverty and illiteracy to mobilise voters with food items such as rice, seasoning, and money, with the assumption that the people are more likely to vote for a politician who influences them with food than one who only brings messages of hope. This practice of using food to mobilize voters is commonly described as "stomach infrastructure" (Okoi & Iwara, 2021).

It is however imperative to state that Nigeria's democracy has a long history, as it has election challenges resulting in election security threats. On 1 October 1960, the Federation of Nigeria gained her independence from Britain and became a member state of the Commonwealth of Nations (CON). The independent Nigeria had the founder of the Northern People's Congress (NPC), Abubakar Tafawa Balewa as the Prime Minister; and Dr. Benjamin Nnamdi Azikiwe, the leader of the National Council of Nigeria and Cameroon (NCNC) appointed the Governor-General (the representative of Queen Elizabeth II) on 16 November 1960. On October 1, 1963, the Federal Republic of Nigeria was created with Balewa as the first Prime Minister, and Azikiwe as the President. On 8 December 1964, President Azikiwe dissolves the House of Representatives. On 30 December 1964 and 18 March 1965, parliamentary elections were conducted with NPC having 162 seats out of 312 in the House of Representatives, while NCNC won 84 seats in the House of Representatives. The United Progressive Grand Alliance (UPGA) boycotted the parliamentary elections (Okoi & Iwara, 2021).

On 11 October 1965, Chief Samuel Akintola of the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) was re-elected as the Premier of Western Region. The post election violence that follows the victory of Akintola led to the killing of 160 civilians and 7 police officers. On 12 January 1966, 20 civilians were also killed in another political violence in Ilesha. This multidimensional electoral security challenge in Nigeria is the reason Omotola (2010:535) observes that election has been one of the main problems of democratisation process in Nigeria. Since independence, the nation has been struggling to sustain its pursuit of democracy and good governance. Development has been so daunting to the extent that all previous attempts at democratic transition have been futile. This is evident in the First Republic (1960-1966), and Second Republic (1979-1983), and the abortion of the Third Republic through the annulment of 12th June 1993 presidential election (Omotola, 2010; Clay, 2024).

Since the restoration of democracy in Nigeria on 29th of May 1999, the electoral body (the INEC) has been saddle with the conduct of free, fair and credible elections. Other functions of the electoral umpire as contained in Section 15, Part 1 of the Third Schedule of the 1999 Constitution (as amended) and Section 2 of the Electoral Act 2010 (as amended) are to organise, undertake and supervise all elections to the office of the President and Vice-President, the Governors and Deputy Governors of a State, and members of the Senate and House of Representatives, and House of Assembly of each States of the federation. The electoral umpire is also saddled with the registration of political parties in accordance with the provisions of the 1999 Constitution and Act of the National Assembly; monitoring of organisation and operation of political parties, including their finances, conventions, congresses, and party primaries. Other functions of INEC include arrangement of annual examination and auditing of the funds and accounts of political parties, and publish a report on such examination and audit for public information; arrangement and conduct of the registration of persons qualified to vote and preparation, maintenance and revision of registered voters for the purpose of any election under the constitution; monitoring political campaigns and provision of rules and regulations which shall govern the political parties; conduct of voter and civic education; and promotion of sound democratic election processes, and conduct of referendum required pursuant to the provision of the 1999 constitution or any other law or Act of the National Assembly (ChannelsTV, 2019; Nairaland Forum, 2024).

The violence that followed the First Republic elections was the reason for the military coup led by Major Chukwuma Nzeogwu and Major Emmanuel Ifeajuna, deposing and killing of the then Prime Minister Abubakar Tafawa Balewa on 15 January 1966. Consequently, there was a counter coup of 28 July 1966, interpreted by critiques as a reaction to the killings of Northern elites and politicians by some soldiers from Eastern Nigeria, a development that saw the country divided along ethnic, tribal and religious lines. Since the restoration of civil rule in 1999 which ushered in the Fourth Republic, there are a number of electoral reforms, some of which created electoral processes that were confronted with challenges, especially in the conduct of general elections (Clay, 2024). As election environments in Nigeria under the Fourth Republic are volatile, conducting elections constitutes a nightmare for the election managers, political parties, candidates, the electorates, and other important stakeholders in the country. Aside the 2023 general elections conducted by INEC, the 2024 Edo and Ondo States governorship elections templates to test the sanctity of the electoral process and the critical role that each of the members of the society, from voters to INEC officials, and security agencies to the civil society organisations played in fortifying the foundation of democracy in Nigeria. The trend of electoral violence significantly moved from the polling units to the collation centers even with the use of Bi-model Voting Accreditation System (BVAS) and the presence of security personnel (Cleen Foundation, 2024).

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a historical research design, relying exclusively on secondary data sourced from existing literature such as academic journals, textbooks, government publications, newspapers, magazines, internet materials, and university libraries in Nigeria. This design enabled a qualitative examination and interpretation of past and present events in order to understand the phenomenon under investigation and its contemporary implications. Data collected were critically examined, authenticated, and systematically organized before being analyzed qualitatively in line with the research questions, allowing for objective evaluation, logical deductions, and the formulation of informed conclusions and policy recommendations.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: Extent to which the Security Agencies have Effectively Policed Elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

Since the transition to civilian rule on 29 May 1999, Nigeria has experienced uninterrupted democratic elections. Security agencies have been tasked with maintaining election security, yet their effectiveness is often questioned due to involvement of some personnel in electoral malpractice. Nevertheless, their role remains crucial given the numerous security challenges since 1999. Afolabi (2018) noted that Nigerian elections are often violent due to politicians' ethnic and power-based competition. Electoral violence includes ballot box snatching, rigging, intimidation, and manipulation of security agencies against opponents (Afolabi, 2012; Oni, Chidozie & Agbude, 2013). The Nigeria Police Force (NPF) and NSCDC are primarily responsible for election security, providing intelligence, monitoring campaigns, protecting materials, and responding to incidents before, during, and after elections (Abdussobur & Yagboyaju, 2019; Nwigwe, 2024). CLEEN Foundation (2023) emphasized that security measures in the 2023 elections were critical to election management, while transitions since 1999 have depended on the combined efforts of security agencies and INEC. Over time, experiences from 1999, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, and 2023 elections show evolving strategies such as inter-agency coordination, intelligence sharing, and military deployment to ensure election security (Olajide, 2025; INEC, 2023).

Research Question 2: Problems Created by Security Agencies during Election Policing in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

Security agencies have sometimes undermined the electoral process. Cases of bias, intimidation, and collusion with ruling parties have been reported in elections from 2003 to 2023 (Olurode &

Hammanga, 2013; Nwambuko & Nnaeto, 2024). Examples include snatching election materials, harassing opposition supporters, misuse of security personnel, and over-deployment creating fear rather than protection (Human Rights Watch, 2004; Mathias & Alioune, 2010). The negative actions of some officers have affected voter turnout, election outcomes, and public trust. Recurrent allegations include partisanship, abuse of power, and failure to prosecute electoral offenders. Even with legal frameworks and electronic voting systems, instances of security complicity in electoral malpractices continue to undermine democracy in Nigeria (Nwosu, 2023; Rosenau, Mushen & McQuaid, 2015).

Research Question 3: Challenges Facing Security Agencies in Policing Elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic.

Security agencies face multiple challenges in election policing. These include limited resources, inadequate equipment, insufficient training, corruption, poor intelligence gathering, and inter-agency rivalry (Mathias & Alioune, 2010; Raji, Adegboyega & Olatunji, 2020). Political influence on postings undermines neutrality, while rising insecurity from terrorism, insurgency, banditry, and separatist movements stretches personnel thin (Adekeye & Chima, 2022). Other challenges include abduction of INEC officials, fake security personnel, private militias, cyber threats, and the centralization of law enforcement under the federal government (Ikenga & Obagbinoko, 2017; Ugwu & Omotola, 2022; Nwosu, 2023). Despite these obstacles, security personnel remain necessary to protect electoral materials, officials, and voters before, during, and after elections.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Extent to which the Security Agencies have Effectively Policed Elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

Since the transition to civilian rule on 29 May 1999, Nigeria has experienced uninterrupted democratic elections. Security agencies have been tasked with election policing, but their effectiveness before, during, and after elections has often been questioned. Despite persistent electoral violence, the roles of security agencies are sometimes underestimated, partly due to involvement of some personnel in election malpractices. Nonetheless, their contributions remain critical given Nigeria's complex security challenges (Afolabi, 2018; Norman, 2010; Olurode, 2013). Electoral violence, including ballot box snatching, vote rigging, underage voting, intimidation, and manipulation of security agencies, is often fueled by high-stakes political competition (Afolabi, 2012; Afolabi, 2014; Oni, Chidozie & Agbude, 2013). While the Nigerian Police Force (NPF) leads law enforcement, agencies such as the NSCDC support election policing amid a politically charged environment (Abdussobur & Yagboyaju, 2019). Security agencies play crucial roles in monitoring campaign rallies, preventing violent escalation, safeguarding electoral materials, conducting intelligence and risk assessments, responding to urgent incidents, supporting voter education, and facilitating post-election investigations (Nwigwe, 2024; CLEEN Foundation, 2023). Over the years, their efforts have contributed to relatively peaceful transitions despite allegations of bias, abuse, and militarization of elections (Olajide, 2025). Significant events illustrate evolving roles: in 1999, the NPF maintained law and order with military support in volatile areas; in 2007, agencies were mobilized amid widespread unrest; in 2011, increased violence in northern states necessitated stronger inter-agency coordination; in 2015 and 2019, security agencies faced insurgency and terrorism challenges; and in 2023, despite sporadic violence, their presence helped prevent large-scale conflicts (Ukiwo, 2007; INEC, 2023; Amnesty International, 2023; Civil Society Situation Room, 2023).

Problems Created by Security Agencies during Elections Policing in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

While security agencies are necessary for maintaining law and order, their involvement has also raised concerns. Some personnel have been accused of partisan behavior, intimidation, and complicity in electoral fraud, which undermines democratic governance (Human Rights Watch, 2023; Iyare, 2018). Incidents of bias, harassment, manipulation, over-deployment, and direct participation in electoral malpractice have occurred repeatedly in elections from 2003 to 2023, including Ekiti (2014, 2018), Edo (2016, 2020), Kogi (2019), and Cross River (2019) elections (Nwosu, 2023; Eja, 2021;

Nwambuko & Nnaeto, 2024). Such actions, combined with corruption, inadequate training, and lack of resources, have weakened the ability of security agencies to protect voters, officials, and materials effectively (Rosenau, Mushen & McQuaid, 2015). Security personnel remain crucial in preventing large-scale violence, protecting electoral materials, and ensuring the continuity of democratic processes.

Challenges Facing Security Agencies in Policing Elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

The police and other security agencies face numerous challenges in election policing. These include limited manpower, inadequate equipment, poor infrastructure, corruption, insufficient training, poor intelligence gathering, inter-agency rivalry, and bureaucratic constraints (Mathias & Alioune, 2010; Albert, 2007; TMG, 2013; Raji, Adegboyega & Olatunji, 2020). Political influence affects deployment, often favoring the ruling party, while rising insecurity—terrorism, banditry, separatist movements, and kidnapping—limits the number of personnel available for elections (Azom, Nwosu & Odigbo, 2022; Adekeye & Chima, 2022). Fake security personnel, abductions of electoral officials, cyber threats, and electronic manipulation further complicate election policing (Ikenga & Obagbinoko, 2017; Ugwu & Omotola, 2022). Centralized command and lack of functional autonomy reduce effectiveness, and multidimensional security threats continue to undermine policing. Nevertheless, security personnel remain essential for safeguarding election materials, officials, and the voting process in Nigeria (Adekeye & Chima, 2022).

CONCLUSION

The policing of elections by security agencies in Nigeria's Fourth Republic has been both critical and complex. Since the return to civilian rule in 1999, security personnel, especially the Nigerian Police Force and NSCDC, have played indispensable roles in maintaining law and order before, during, and after elections. Their efforts in intelligence gathering, crowd control, protection of electoral materials, and crisis management have contributed significantly to the continuity of democratic governance in Nigeria. However, these achievements are often overshadowed by allegations of partisanship, abuse of power, inadequate training, corruption, and operational challenges, which have sometimes fueled electoral violence and undermined public trust in the democratic process. Political manipulation, resource constraints, and multidimensional security threats—including insurgency, separatist movements, and banditry—further complicate their ability to perform effectively. In conclusion, while security agencies remain essential to Nigeria's electoral process, their effectiveness depends on professional integrity, adequate resourcing, neutrality, and functional autonomy from political influence. Strengthening these areas will ensure that elections are conducted in a peaceful, credible, and transparent manner, thereby consolidating democracy in Nigeria's Fourth Republic.

REFERENCES

- Abdussobur, A., & Yagboyaju, D. (2019). *Role of security agencies in election management in Nigeria*. *Journal of Political Studies*, 12(3), 45–62.
- Afilabi, O. (2012). *Electoral violence in Nigeria: Causes and effects*. Lagos: Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research.
- Afolabi, O. (2014). *Electoral violence and security challenges in Nigeria's democracy*. Abuja: National Democratic Institute.
- Afolabi, O. (2018). *Political competition and electoral violence in Nigeria*. *African Journal of Political Science*, 8(2), 78–95.
- Albert, I. O. (2007). *Security challenges and democratic consolidation in Nigeria*. Ibadan: University Press.
- Ali, A., & Ali, B. (2022). *Elections and democratic governance in modern society*. *Journal of Governance and Democracy*, 1(1), 1–15.
- Amnesty International. (2023). *Election security and human rights in Nigeria*. Amnesty International Report.

- Alao, A. (2021). Electoral violence and democratic governance in Nigeria. *Journal of African Politics*, 15(3), 310–330.
- Appadorai, A. (2004). *The substance of politics* (7th ed.). New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Azom, J., Nwosu, P., & Odigbo, K. (2022). *Security challenges in election management in Nigeria*. Abuja: Centre for Democratic Studies.
- Cleen Foundation. (2023). *Post-election security assessment report*. Lagos: Cleen Foundation.
- Clay, R. (2024). *History of elections and democracy in Nigeria*. Lagos: Academic Press.
- ChannelsTV. (2019). *Functions of INEC in Nigeria's democratic process*. Retrieved from <https://www.channelstv.com>
- Civil Society Situation Room. (2023). *Election observation report 2023 general elections in Nigeria*. Abuja: Civil Society Situation Room.
- Dibie, R. (2012). *Political parties and democracy in Nigeria*. Lagos: University Press.
- Eja, E. (2021). *The impact of security agencies on electoral credibility in Nigeria*. *International Journal of Political Studies*, 5(2), 45–60.
- Erunke, E. (2012). *Military coups and democratic instability in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books.
- Edirinverere, J. (2023). *Electoral processes and security challenges in Nigeria's Fourth Republic*. *Journal of African Governance*, 9(1), 22–38.
- Hoffmann, L., & Wallace, R. (2023). *Nigeria's democratic consolidation since 1999*. *African Journal of Political Studies*, 14(1), 55–70.
- Human Rights Watch. (2004). *Election violence and security in Nigeria*. Human Rights Watch Report.
- Human Rights Watch. (2023). *Partisanship and electoral malpractice in Nigeria*. Human Rights Watch Report.
- Ikenga, C., & Obagbinoko, T. (2017). *Election security and challenges in Nigeria's democracy*. *Journal of Security Studies*, 4(1), 10–28.
- Iyare, T. (2018). *The role of security agencies in Nigerian elections*. Lagos: Nigerian Institute of Political Studies.
- Matthew, O. (2023). *Military involvement in election security in Nigeria*. Abuja: Defence and Security Journal.
- McLean, I., & McMillan, A. (2010). *The concise Oxford dictionary of politics* (3rd ed.). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- McMillan, A. (2010). *Political structures and party politics in Nigeria*. Lagos: University Press.
- Meredith, M. (2005). *The fate of Africa: A history of fifty years of independence*. London: Public Affairs.
- Mustapha, A. R., & Isah, A. (2018). *Ethnic politics and party formation in Nigeria*. *African Journal of Political Science*, 13(2), 115–130.
- Nairaland Forum. (2024). *INEC's role in Nigerian elections*. Retrieved from <https://www.nairaland.com>
- Nwigwe, E. (2024). *Election policing in Nigeria: Progress and challenges*. *Journal of Governance and Security*, 3(1), 50–68.
- Nwambuko, P., & Nnaeto, O. (2024). *Security agencies and electoral malpractice in Nigeria's Fourth Republic*. *Nigerian Journal of Politics*, 7(1), 101–120.
- Nwosu, J. (2023). *Challenges of security agencies in electoral management in Nigeria*. Lagos: Centre for Democracy and Development.
- Olajide, T. (2025). *Inter-agency coordination and election security in Nigeria*. *Journal of Political Studies*, 18(2), 75–92.
- Olurode, L., & Hammanga, I. (2013). *Election management and the role of security agencies in Nigeria*. Abuja: Centre for Governance Studies.
- Okereka, E., Efebeh, T., Ikenga, C., & Oluka, E. (2020). *Political parties and democratic consolidation in Nigeria*. Lagos: University Press.

- Okoi, P., & Iwara, A. (2021). *Stomach infrastructure and voter mobilization in Nigeria*. African Journal of Governance, 6(1), 25–42.
- Okolo, A. (2002). *Democracy and electoral processes in Africa*. Lagos: Macmillan Nigeria.
- Openiyi, O. (2020). *Military intervention and political development in Nigeria*. Journal of African Politics, 12(2), 33–50.
- Omotola, J. S. (2010). *Elections and democratic consolidation in Nigeria*. African Journal of Political Science, 5(4), 525–540.
- Oni, S., Chidozie, O., & Agbude, D. (2013). *Electoral violence and voter behavior in Nigeria*. Lagos: National Political Science Review, 3(1), 18–34.
- Oyewole, F. (2020). *Military involvement in election security in Nigeria*. Abuja: Defence Studies Journal.
- Raji, A., Adegboyega, T., & Olatunji, F. (2020). *Challenges of policing elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic*. International Journal of Security Studies, 6(2), 34–52.
- Rosenau, J., Mushen, R., & McQuaid, J. (2015). *Security and elections in developing democracies*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- TG Monitoring Group (TMG). (2013). *Election security challenges in Nigeria*. Lagos: TMG Publications.
- Ugwu, C., & Omotola, J. (2022). *Electoral threats and security management in Nigeria*. Nigerian Journal of Democracy, 8(1), 60–82.
- Ukiwo, U. (2007). *Political violence and election management in Nigeria*. African Affairs, 106(425), 323–342.